

METHODS OF LEARNING MUSIC LITERACY DURING MUSIC LESSONS

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Annotation: In this thesis, opinions are given about the methods of improving music literacy and teaching music theory in music classes.

Key words: Music education, music theory, note, sound line, musical key symbols.

Introduction:

Scholars of the past have always emphasized the incomparable importance of music, its divinity, and its connection with spirituality in the formation of a person as a person. Alisher Navoi, the genius of Uzbek poetry, expresses his wonderful thoughts about this in one of his prose works: "A singer who increases happiness, a musician who spreads sorrow, emotional people and people of pain sacrifice their lives for both of these. As they sing with a gentle melody, what wonder if the cash lives of the listeners are sacrificed to the tune? After all, the soul is strengthened by a good melody, and the soul is nourished by a good voice.

Music serves to form the spiritual, artistic and moral culture of the young generation, to implement the upbringing of national pride, patriotism, sophistication and creativity, to expand the worldview, to develop independence and initiative. Great educational opportunities of music are revealed only on the basis of serious professional training of the teacher, constant attention to the personality of the student and the development of his musical and creative abilities. In addition, one of the important factors determining the effectiveness of music education is the level of theoretical development of musical methodical issues and its connection with practice. The methodology of music education determines the specific characteristics, goals and tasks, laws, theoretical foundations and methodological directions of music education in secondary schools. In music education pedagogy, for many years, the lack of sufficient textbooks or training manuals in the Uzbek language on the subject of music teaching methodology has had a negative effect on the quality of the personnel training process. We believe that this manual will serve to improve the methodological training of future music teachers and young professionals. The presentation contains material on the

main problems of music education in secondary schools. This material was created on the basis of the author's many years of work experience at the university and school, as well as the study of a number of scientific and methodological literature in this field. Theoretical foundations of teaching music in schools, school. The uniqueness of music lessons as an educational subject, modern requirements for a music teacher, and the main and special methods of music education will be highlighted. The content of these sections is the "foundation" of the teaching methodology and helps students to understand the basis of musical-pedagogical activity.

Music literacy is one of the important sections of music lessons. Music theory improves the students' level. Music literacy cultivates musical will and conscious attitude, helps to understand the meaning of music, and most importantly, it affects the formation of skills of singing and playing according to the note and the development of harmonic ability.

The main methodological requirement for studying music theory is the direct application of acquired musical knowledge, which helps in skills such as analyzing a musical work, writing notes, conducting, playing a musical instrument, and singing.

Music - the expression through sound - is subject to certain rules that connect the means of expression of music. These rules emerged as a result of the centuries-old experience of folk and classical music.

Musical expression and means of expression are called musical elements. Music theory sets itself the task of studying musical works-melody. In order to generalize the acquired knowledge, information is provided about each musical element (key, tonality, meter, rhythm, interval, chord, etc.), it should be remembered that it has the power of expression only when connected with other means of musical expression.

In addition to the above-mentioned main task, music theory aims to help students in their major, which helps them to master musical notation.

Elementary knowledge and listening skills acquired by students in analyzing a piece of music (determining the melody of a piece of music and the structure of certain parts) add diversity to their independent work in their specialty and, in turn, allow students to understand a piece of music. it also helps to reveal its content correctly when performing.

Along with other subjects, music theory helps to increase the general musical and cultural level of students. In studying music theory, it is not enough to get acquainted with the basic rules from a practical point of view, it

is necessary to study this science comprehensively and in depth. Regular work on the exercises helps to further consolidate the acquired knowledge and skills.

It is necessary to approach didactic principles in learning this subject. Education should be based on scientific, consistent and systematic principles. The transition from simple to complex means conscious repetition and consolidation of the material, it is necessary to combine individual treatment with team in education. Developing students' listening skills is one of the main tasks of a music teacher.

The word "sound" has two meanings. The first is physical sound, and the second is sensory sound.

1. The vibration of the string of a musical instrument is called vibration and is called a sound wave.

2. Sound waves are received by the hearing organ and affect the brain through its system.

Musical sound is different, but our ears distinguish between musical sound and noisy sound.

Noisy sounds include sounds that do not have a clear pitch, such as crackling, squeaking, humming, and hissing.

Musical sound has three physical properties: loudness and timbre. In addition, the extension of the music sound is also very important. The pitch depends on the speed of the vibration, the slower the vibration, the lower the sound. Loudness depends on the strength of the vibration, the greater the amplitude of the vibration, the louder the sound, and vice versa.

The duration of the sound depends on the duration of the vibration. High tones are produced by additional vibration. Its ballads are different because the speed of their vibration is different.

Musical system

In the system, the sounds are placed according to their height, and the sound in the sound line is called its step. The music system has 88 different sounds. All sounds have 16 to 4176 vibrations per second. The musical system has seven independent names for the main steps of the sound series. DO. RE. MI. FA. SOL Lya. SI. These sounds correspond to the white keys of the piano.

The name of these 7 main steps is repeated in the sound line, and in a way it includes all sounds.

The range of sounds of the same name is called an octave. There are 9 octaves on the piano and their names are as follows. Subcontroktava, kontraktava, major octave, minor octave, first octave, second octave, third octave, fourth octave, and fifth octave.

In a musical system, the absolute pitch of the sounds is precisely adjusted and interconnected, called musical tuning.

The musical sound is based on the sound of the first octave Lya vibrating 440 times per second. In the musical system, each octave is divided into 12 equal semitones and is called a tempered note. A semitone is the smallest interval in the musical system. Two semitones are called a whole tone.

There are two semitones and five whole tones in the vocal range. They are located in the following order.

DO RE MI FA SOL LYa SI DO 1t 1t 0.5t 1 1 1 0.5t

Whole tones are divided into semitones. The pitch can be raised or lowered by each major step of the scale. The sounds corresponding to raised and lowered steps are derivative steps. The name of the derivative steps comes from the main steps.

If the main step is raised by a semitone, the word sharp is used, and if it is decreased by a semitone, the word bemol is added. If the double sharp is lowered by two semitones, then the double sharp is raised by two semitones and is called an alteration. The word alteration means change.

SIGNS OF ALTERATION

The raising or lowering of the main steps is called alteration.

There are 5 types of alteration signs.

Sharp - # - raises the note by 0.5 tones Flat - b - lowers the note by 0.5 tones Double sharp - x - raises the note by 1 tone Double flat - bb - lowers the note by 1 tone Blank - cancels the signs.

The symbols placed after the key are called key alteration symbols. Key alternations remain valid for the duration of the piece, while accidentals remain valid for one bar.

Are the sounds enharmonic? Letter system The equality of pitches with the same height but different names and spellings is called enharmonism of sounds. Each sound can be a semitone lower or higher than itself.

For example; fa-sharp or si-flat. The derivative step can be the same as the base step. For example; si diez do, fa bemol mi or barabari can be lowered or raised. For example; fa double sharp - sol, mi double, free - d.

Diatonic and chromatic.

Half tones and whole tones.

A semitone formed between two adjacent steps of a sound series is called a diatonic semitone. These include mi-fa and si-do. Diatonic semitones also occur between raised or lowered derivative steps.

For example:

A chromatic semitone is when a semitone is formed between the rising or

falling of the main step.

For example:

Diatonic whole tones are called intervals do-re, re-mi, fa-sol, sol-lya, lya-si, and in addition to these, two derivatives can also appear between steps. For example:

Chromatic whole tones are said to occur when the main step is doubled or diminished. For example.

KEYS

The specific pitch of sounds is determined by a special symbol, and this

symbol is called a key. The clef is placed on the main bars at the beginning of the note track. The note on this line determines the pitch.

Currently, three types of keys are used.

- 1) Treble clef (treble clef)

- 2) Bass clef (F clef)

- 3) Alt and Tenor key (C key)

The alto clef is used for alto and trombone instruments. Tenor clef is used for bassoon and trombone instruments. In the past, there were many types of keys.

C - soprano key is placed on the 1st line. The 2nd line has the messo soprano clef and the 5th line has the Baritone clef, which correspond to the human voice range and have many additional lines..

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